

Guide to protocolize processes of femicide identification for later registration

Methodological document

WITH THE SUPPORT OF

1.Introduction: About the need for this protocol

Women are subject to multiple forms of discrimination that violate principles of equal rights and respect for human dignity. The Committee for the Elimination of Discrimination against Women (the CEDAW Committee) identified the gender-based violence as one of the manifestations of discrimination whose main cause is inequality. That is, asymmetric power relations between men and women they constitute “a form of discrimination that prevents that [women] enjoy equal rights and freedoms with men ”(CEDAW 1994¹)

According to the Gender Equality Observatory of the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC) in 2016, according to official information provided by the countries, a total of 1,831 women of 16 countries in the region (13 in Latin America and 3 in the Caribbean) were victims of femicide. As mentioned in that same report, “(...) in addition to the measures concrete prevention, care, protection and repair, another challenge in this path towards the eradication of violence is precisely the availability of information ”(ECLAC 2016²).

In this context, this document aims to guide a better record of deaths of women due to gender.³ Due to the relevance to have not only that data, but also protocols that allow us understand what we are counting, several exercises have been made to improve the registration of femicides⁴. Some of the most outstanding adaptations of the Latin American Protocol Model of Investigation of Violent Deaths of Women by Gender Reasons (Latin American Model Protocol) are the protocol of the Unit Prosecutor Specialized in Violence Against Women (UFEM) and the Ministry Public Prosecutor of the Province of Buenos Aires, in Argentina⁵. This guide and the standardization proposal that goes with it⁶, present a regional approach, this guide go beyond the legislation of a specific country or administrative unit, so references to any of them are not included.

¹ Cedaw, C. (1994). General Recommendation No. 19, Violence against women. General recommendations adopted by the Committee for the Elimination of Discrimination against Women.

² Gender Equality Observatory of Latin America and the Caribbean (2018) Femicide. <https://oig.cepal.org/es/indicadores/feminicidio>

³ Cis or trans women

⁴ Although, femicide and/or feminicide are not synonymous for the purposes of this protocol, both are understood as the death of a woman (cis or trans) because of her gender.

⁵ This Protocol and the standard are based on the previous work carried out for the Latin American Protocol Model, the Convention of Belém do Pará and the Bogotá Protocol, among other sources consulted.

⁶ At the beginning of 2017, due to the relevance of the problem of femicide for the region, ILDA, with the support of IDRC and Fundación Avina, began an exploratory study in order to understand how data production and its use can contribute to understand and, eventually, combat femicides in Latin America. After the first stage of reflection and development of the draft, of the regional feminicide standard, it was considered necessary to begin with the stage of implementation and feedback with the actors in the field. In the process we find in the Open Justice Program of the Ministry of Justice and Human Rights of Argentina an ally willing to collaborate with the implementation of the first pilot. This document is a product of that exercise.

There are multiple ways to carry out the previous processes, to register the data, which allow to characterize femicides. The guide intends to protocolize these processes so that the registered cases, according to the standard, have a common identification methodology. Identifying a femicide is a complex task, which depends on legal and empirical variables in a given district⁷. Public officials working on the qualification, registration and storage of femicide data in different districts of Latin America, have agreed that this process has been done, in many cases, without a protocol and there is not always a unified criterion about when to use the concept of femicide⁸. Having a unified collection/production process will improve and encourage analysis and use of data.

Generally, there is no gender approach in prosecutors and courts which, added to the work overload, impacts on the qualification of the event in the judicial records. This situation is evident when judicial agents may get the same sentence for the crime even if they are not officially qualified as femicide. As an example, a homicide aggravated by the relationship between victim and perpetrator obtains a similar punitive result although it is not sustained on aspects of gender violence. This situation forces the register the data to look more closely at the cases, since, sometimes, this type of qualifications make invisible, at first sight, femicides.

The gender-based training of those who collect data within the system, as well as those in connected systems (eg. police or women's violence offices), is presented as necessary. It also demonstrates the need to generate common criteria for what is known as linked femicide and to include the LGBTIQ community in the records.

2. Protocolization of femicides: Conceptual Framework

The starting point is femicide understood as the violent death of one or more women for gender reasons. While all femicides can be qualified as homicides, not all homicides of women are likely to be qualified as femicides. The reason is that it may not be related to the condition of being a woman or not being motivated by gender reasons.

The figure of "femicide" constitutes the most extreme form of violence against women. That is to say, they reinforce and perpetuate the patterns that culturally have been assigned to what it means to be a woman: subordination, weakness, feelings, delicacy, femininity, etc. According to the Latin American Model Protocol, femicide can occur in three areas or contexts: intimate and family, sexual, and group. Some models include transvesticide/transfemicide as a fourth context but, as we understand that gender is self-identifying, these cases are included in any of the three previous areas, according to the characteristics of the fact.

⁷ Understand by district to a country, state or province, depending on the application of the standard.

⁸ The recent World Report of the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2018) specifically recognizes this point on page

We propose, based on the protocol developed by the Public Prosecution Ministry of the Province of Buenos Aires⁹, four indicators that summarize in a simple manner the majority of the causes that allow us to understand when we face a femicide.

I. Previous relationship between the victim and the aggressor

One of the contexts of femicides is the intimate and familiar: they occur in the scope of couple, ex-partner and family ties between victim and perpetrator. According to the Latin American Protocol Model, some factors at risk are: pregnancy of the victim, separation or will of the victim of ending the relationship, violence against other women in the family.

They present some characteristic in the subsequent behavior of the offender (such as suicide/voluntary surrender), the happening of the event in front of the children and/or other relatives, the use of domestic tools and/or hands for execution, etc.

II. Sexual Violence

According to the Latin American Protocol Model, it is understood as “sexual violence” any action aimed at violating a woman’s sexual or reproductive freedom and integrity. It is expressed in direct or symbolic sexual attacks, both consummated and tempted.

III. Violence aggravation (and/or)

In this case, the two contexts previously mentioned can be included, as well as femicides in organized crime contexts. This last context refers to those femicides that emerge within the framework of the use of women as merchandise, as product of revenge between bands, or in response to their deviation in relation to what is expected of their behavior according to status of your gender.

IV. Previous Complaints

Indicates the existence of a previous path of violence that can be framing one of the three above-mentioned contexts.

While these options are not exhaustive or exclusive, the presence of one of these indicators in the determination of the fact allows to guide, in a very accurate way, the registration of femicides in a given district. The sources of production and data collection will be adapted in each district.

However, it is important to have clear rules of governance and ownership of the data, its classification and its subsequent publication. In this sense, it is key that the legal typification of each case is also enhanced by the information collected from other sources to complement and/or confirm it. It is also essential that the agency responsible for each district

⁹ That document was prepared based on the study of gender and femicide perspectives, its theoretical and methodological currents and the contribution of different models, including: the Latin American Protocol for the Investigation of Violent Deaths of Women for Gender Reasons (femicide / feminicide) prepared by the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) with the support of the United Nations Entity for Gender Equality and the Empowerment of Women (UN Women).

define a timeline, select the sources of information, the techniques to be used and the type of analysis to be applied.

3. Steps for effective registration

After collecting information from various sources and with the previous work carried out by the Public Prosecutor's Office of the Province of Buenos Aires (Argentina), we suggest a series of steps to facilitate the protocolization of the identification process, registration and subsequent update.

1) Quarterly Survey

- a) A quarterly list of violent deaths of women perpetrated by men or with unidentified aggressor is made. From this list, each case is analyzed in order to determine femicides according to established indicators.
- b) Cases are categorized as "PENDING" when it is NOT possible to determine if any of the indicators are present, in order to review them in the next quarter, hoping it is possible collect more information and determine if it is a femicide.
- c) Cases are categorized as "NOT FEMICIDE" those in which you can clearly determine that none of the indicators are present.
- d) Cases categorized as "FEMICIDE" are the ones where one or more of the indicators are present.
- e) The search of all the fields of analysis is carried out in the standardization proposal (see annex 1 in this document or its development version: <https://datosabiertos.org/en/estandardatosfemicidios/>) in cases identified as femicides.

2) Annual Review

- a) A new list is produced with the investigations which have been initiated during the year of analysis. All the cases that registered at least one homicide is included. The same analysis and debugging procedure from the quarterly survey is performed (as described in the previous point).
- b) This information is compared with the one obtained in each quarter analyzed.
- c) From this, cases not previously identified are included and the same femicide identification procedure is performed.

3) Unification

- a) Quarterly databases and the annual review are unified.
- b) Fields are homogenized and assigned according to parameterized fields.

4) Control and Validation

- a) A review of all investigations is carried out in order to verify their correct identification and the surveyed fields.
- b) Journalistic articles and other relevant sources are tracked (eg online femicide maps) to identify possible femicides, as a part of a parallel control mechanism.

The following flow map illustrates how to proceed with data collection according to this protocol.

Annex 1: Variables and coding of observations

Here is a Beta version of the work done in terms of the definition of variables to register and a contribution on the codifications that should accompany them.

Variables to register

These variables arose from a participatory process that began in 2017, which included numerous specialists in gender and civic technology. It is a process in constant evolution.

Entity	Code	Title	Definition
Accused	ID	ID	Only identifier of this record in the system
Accused	name	Name	Complete name of the person
Accused	gender	Gender Identity	Gender identity of the person according to the code list
Accused	Sexual orientation	Sexual Orientation	Sexual orientation of the person according to the code list
Accused	age	Age	Age at the time of the event
Accused	placeBirth	Place of Birth	Place of Birth.
Accused	nationality	Nationality	Nationality
Accused	education	Level of Education	Level of education according to the code list.
Accused	occupation	Occupation	Occupation
Accused	Address	Address	Address of the aggressor
Accused	placeResidency	Place of Residency	Place of residency

Accused	MigratoryCondition	Migratory condition	Migratory Condition
Accused	ethnicity	Ethnicity	Ethnicity
Accused	LegalSituation	Legal Situation	Legal Situation: processed, condemned, under investigation, according to the code list.
Accused	Conjugal situation	Conjugal situation	Conjugal situation of the aggressor without having to be related to the victim
Accused	WeaponcarrierPermit	Weapon Carrier Permit	Weapon Carrier Permit.
Accused	Affiliation SecurityForce	Affiliation to the security force	Affiliation to the security force
Accused	Previous record	Previous Record	Previous record of violence or other crimes
Accused	suicide	Suicide	Suicide, or attempt of suicide.
Accused	generator	Data generator	Information to identify the data generator
Victim	ID	ID	Only identifier of this record in the system.
Victim	name	Name	Complete Name of the person
Victim	gender	Gender Identity	Gender identity of the person according to the code list
Victim	Sexual Orientation	Sexual Orientation	Sexual Orientation according to the code list
Victim	age	age	Age at the moment of the event
Victim	placeBirth	Place of Birth	Place of birth.
Victim	nationality	Nationality	Nationality

Victim	education	Level of education	Level of education according to the code list
Victim	occupation	Occupation	Occupation
Victim	address	Address	Victim's Address.
Victim	PlaceResidency	Place of Residency	Place of Residency.
Victim	disability	Disability	Disability (if it applies) of the victim
Victim	MigratoryCondition	Migratory Condition	Migratory Condition
Victim	ethnicity	Ethnicity	Ethnicity
Victim	ProtectionMeasures	Protection Measures	Protection and prevention measures.
Victim	PreviousComplaint	Previous complaints	Previous complaints of the victim.
Victim	children	Having Children	Value Yes/No to having children.
Victim	generator	Data generator organism	information to identify the data generator
Event	place	Place	Place of the event.
Event	VictimType	VictimType	Victim relation to the event according to the code list
Event	RelationType	Relation type	Relation or family ties between victim and aggressor.
Event	modality	Modality	Existence of weapons or other objects.
Event	SexualAggression	Sexual Aggression	If there was sexual aggression or not.

Event	date	Date	Time and date of the event.
Event	previous Complaints	Previous Complaints	If the aggressor has previous complaints from the victim
Event	LegalProcess	Legal Process	If the process is active or not
Event	generator	Data generator organism	Information to identify the data generator
Place	description	Description	Description
Place	type	Place Type	Place type according to the code list.
Place	address	Address	Address
Place	city	City	City
Place	country	Country	Country
Place	zipCode	Zip Code	Zip Code
Organism	name	Organism	Organism name where the data is generated
Organism	OrganismType	Organism Type	Organism type according to the code list
Organism	role	Role of the person in charge of the data generation	Role of the person capturing data
Organism	contact	Contact	Organization Contact.
Legal Process	situation	Legal Process	Investigation process
Legal Process	Complainant	Complainant	National Identification Document
Legal Process	OpeningDate	Opening Date	Opening Date

Legal Process	peopleInvolved	Number of people involved	Number of People involved
Legal Process	aggravation	Aggravation	Aggravation
Legal Process	parties	Intervening Parties	Intervening Parties
Legal Process	CrimeType	Crime Type	Crime Type
Relation with victim	type	Relation Type	Type of relationship between victim and aggressor
Relation with the victim	details	Details	General observations about the relationship with the victim

Coding of the observations

Some of the variables included in the previous table already have an accepted coding. Some of them are included below as an example.

Gender Identity		
Code	Title	Description
1	Cis Man	Man identified with his gender at birth.
2	Cis Woman	Woman identified with her gender at birth
3	Non Binary	Person that does not identify as woman or man
4	Other	Other gender identity.
5	Unknown	Unknown Gender.
6	Trans woman	Woman that does not identify herself with her gender at birth.
7	Trans man	Man that does not identify with his gender at birth
Modality		
Code	Title	Description

1	Beating	Murdered by beating.
2	Shot to death	Shot to death.
3	Stabbing	Murdered by stabbing.
4	Burnt	Murdered burnt.
5	Choking	Murdered choked.
6	Drowning	Murdered by drowning.
7	Drilled	Murdered by drilling.
8	Ran over	Murdered ran over.
9	Suffocated	Murdered suffocated.
10	Other measures	Murdered by other measures.
11	Unknown	The modality is unknown.

Level of Education

Code	Title	Description
1	Early Childhood	Education in early childhood.
2	Preschool	Below Elementary school.
3	Elementary School	Elementary school.
4	Secondary school	Secondary School.
5	Higher Secondary	Higher Secondary Education
6	Further education	Further education / Vocational education
7	Tertiary	Tertiary/ Higher Education
8	Degree	University degree or equivalent.
9	Masters	Masters level or equivalent.
10	Phd	Phd Level.
11	Unknown	Unknown Education Level.

Sexual Orientation

Code	Title	Description
1	Lesbian	Identified as lesbian.

3	Heterosexual	Identified as heterosexual.
4	Bisexual	Identified as bisexual.
5	Asexual	Identified as asexual.
6	Other	Other sexual orientation.
7	Unknown	Unknown Sexual Orientation.

Legal Situation

Code	Title	Description (according to the legislation of the country, city, or province)
1	Accused	
2	Investigated	
3	Processed	
4	Charged	
5	Condemned	
6	Fugitive	
7	Conditional freedom	
8	Preventive Jail	
9	Other	
10	Unknown	

Organism Type

Code	Title	Description
1	Police	Police Organism including emergency agents.
2	Judicial	National Judicial Organism.
3	Prosecutor	Prosecutor.
4	Health	Health Institution
5	Social Development Ministry	Social Development Ministry
6	Provincial Justice	Judicial Power at a Province level

7	Public Prosecution Ministry	
8	Justice Ministry	Justice Ministry
9	Medicine	Legal Medicine
10	Women Ministry	Woman Ministry
Place Type		
Code	Title	Description
1	Address of the victim	Place of Residency of the victim
2	Address of the aggressor	Place of residency of the aggressor
3	Particular Address	Place of Residency not exclusively of the victim or the aggressor
4	Open Space	Street or public transportation.
5	Job Position	Place where the daily activities are performed
6	Education Institution	Schools or other educational institutions
7	Jail	Jail.
8	Institution	Institutional attention spaces such as hospitals.
9	Other	
10	Unknown	
Relationship Type		
Code	Title	Description
1	Father	Aggressor is father of the victim.
2	Mother	Aggressor is mother of the victim.
3	Stepfather	Aggressor is stepfather of the victim.
4	Stepmother	Aggressor is stepmother of the victim.
5	Tutor	Aggressor is tutor of the victim.
6	Husband/Wife	Aggressor is husband or wife of the victim.
7	Concubine	Aggressor is the concubine of the victim.

8	Boyfriend/Girlfriend	Aggressor is boyfriend or girlfriend of the victim.
9	Lover	Aggressor is lover of the victim.
10	Previous Couple	Previous couple of the victim.
11	Family	Aggressor is family of the victim.
12	Job	Aggressor is an employee or colleague of the victim.
13	Known person	Aggressor is a known person of the victim.
14	Friend	The aggressor is friend of the victim.
15	Other transgressor	Other transgressor known by the victim.
16	Authority	Official Authorities
17	Unknown Person	The aggressor is an unknown person for the victim.
18	Unknown	Unknown relationship.
Victim Type		
Code	Title	Description
1	Main	Main victim of the femicide.
2	Linked	Linked victim of the femicide.